

Recommended citation: Lutsenko, G. V., & Lucenko, G. V. (2018). Project-based learning in automation engineering curriculum. In Clark, R., Munkebo Hussmann, P., Järvinen, H.-M., Murphy, M., & Eтчells Vigild, M. (Eds.), *Creativity, Innovation and Entrepreneurship for Engineering Education Excellence. SEFI 46th Annual Conference* (pp. 1032-1039). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Brussels, Belgium. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14672772.

PROJECT-BASED LEARNING IN AUTOMATION ENGINEERING CURRICULUM

G.V. Lutsenko¹

Associate Professor

Bohdan Khmelnytsky National University of Cherkasy

Cherkasy, Ukraine

E-mail: LutsenkoG@gmail.com

G.V. Lucenko

Professor

Hlukhiv O. Dovzhenko National Pedagogical University

Hlukhiv, Ukraine

E-mail: gr1974@ukr.net

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Skills, Teaching Creativity & Innovation

Keywords: project-based learning, team teaching, human-computer interface, skills

INTRODUCTION

The Ukrainian system of higher engineering education has been undergoing progressing reformation in the recent years. Experts have identified the following most significant driving forces for the transformation processes in the system of higher engineering education [1, 2]:

- Global processes related to the change of the role and place of engineers and engineering at the beginning of the 21st century.
- System changes of approaches to learning and teaching in Ukraine and across the world.
- Economical factors, which in the case of Ukrainian engineering education are closely related to the solution of ongoing issues of laboratory equipment modernisation.

¹ Corresponding Author
G.V. Lutsenko
LutsenkoG@gmail.com

According to the surveys, which were carried out in 2012-2013 [3, 4], Ukrainian stakeholders identified the following skills and abilities whose lack is most significant for Engineering graduates: practically oriented professional skills; problem-solving skills; skills for working with experts and customers from different fields. In addition, stakeholders emphasised the importance of the ability to communicate effectively in foreign languages, analytical skills and abilities related to project management. Moreover, the great problem is to find employees who have acquired knowledge and skills from more than one narrow field.

According to the factors listed above, the development of educational initiatives in the context of the reformation of Ukrainian system of higher education, and approximation to the standards and recommendations of the Bologna Process have been considered as an urgent objective for academic staff and administration of Ukrainian higher educational institutions.

The paper outlines the on-going experience and the first findings concerning the following steps aimed to improve the Automation and Computer-Integrated Technologies (ACIT) degree programme at Bohdan Khmelnytsky National University of Cherkasy (BKNUC):

- Implementation of problem-based and project-based learning as efficient methodologies for the development of a wide range of subject-specific and general skills and abilities.
- Selection of practically oriented projects, which simultaneously helps to solve such pedagogical tasks as contextualisation of the learning process and encouragement of students to participate in applied design and scientific research, as well as urgent university organisational tasks, namely, updating and upgrading of laboratory equipment.
- Using of advanced software allowing to smooth over the lag of technical equipment of Ukrainian engineering departments and, in future, will lead to the full-grown using of emerging technologies.

It should be noted that most Ukrainian authors have maintained a prevalent focus on very particular aspects of discipline projects implementation, staying within the frames of traditional discipline-led approaches. Respectively, the lack of procedures for explicit application of PBL approaches within the context of the Ukrainian system of higher education is noticeable.

1 CURRICULUM DESIGN

1.1 Context and preconditions

BKNUC offers Bachelor of Engineering degree in Automation and Computer-Integrated Technologies (ACIT) with a 4-year normative period of training. Each year, 25 to 30 students holding that degree graduate from the university. Bachelor's thesis is a compulsory part of the curriculum of the ACIT degree programme. According to the traditional for Ukrainian system of higher education approaches and regulatory documents, the bachelor's thesis was treated as an individual learning activity of engineering students. At the same time, the need to prepare students for their future work, which corresponds to the stakeholders' demands, led to the necessity of the inclusion of group student projects as a significant element of the curriculum.

The first experience related to introducing PBL approaches was based mostly on the individual initiatives of teachers [5, 6]. The point was that each member of the Department of ACIT is a scientific advisor to three or four student theses each academic year. Respectively, teams of ACIT students working on mutual engineering projects were organised [7].

Monitoring of the projects is performed through examination of feedback from students and faculty using qualitative methods of collecting, analysing, and presenting data on project activities. The survey is conducted via semi-structured questionnaires covering pedagogical and organisational aspects, with student participation in conferences, startup competitions and the like being viewed as indirect indicators. The main aim of the monitoring is a) to find the

possibilities to improvement of ACIT curriculum in the future; b) to analyse faculty and students PBL experiences including the organization of multidisciplinary projects by collaboration in academic sphere.

1.2. Design of PBL curriculum elements

Problem-based learning and project-based learning are widely used in educational approaches which have both differences and similarities [8, 9]. In our work, we focused on the compliance with the following theoretical and applied principles of PBL [8]: a problem is the starting point of learning process; learning is student-centred; the learning process takes place in small groups of students working with a tutor who acts as a facilitator; self-directed learning in order to acquire new information; multidisciplinary nature of projects.

Introduction of PBL is related to all parts of the curriculum including learning objectives and knowledge, type of projects and problems, progression and size, space and organisation, students' learning, academic staff and facilitation, assessment and evaluation [10]. We used the following model of PBL curriculum, taking into account the necessity to build an integrated approach which engages not only the academic staff but also the administration and local industry representatives. In addition, the monitoring of projects implementation was added as an important element of the learning process organisation (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. PBL curriculum elements (based on [10])

Below we consider the main elements of curriculum in details.

Learning outcomes

While developing the list of learning outcomes and related subject-specific and general competencies we took into account the specificity of the educational programme and general specifications prescribed by the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine. The Tuning list of competencies and Tuning-AHELO engineering competence framework were used [11, 12].

The list of main learning outcomes is as follows:

- To be able to demonstrate comprehensive knowledge and understanding of the scientific and mathematical principles and key aspects of physics, higher mathematics, automation, microprocessor-based systems etc.);
- To be able to apply knowledge and understanding to formulate engineering problems and choose appropriate methods of solution as well as to analyse engineering products, processes and methods;
- To be able to choose and use appropriate methods and techniques of data acquisition systems design to meet defined and specified requirements;

- To be able to select and use appropriate equipment, tools and methods and to demonstrate an understanding of applicable techniques and methods and their limitations;
- To be able to use different sources of information, to analyse and verify information;
- To be able to carry out the planning, management and completion of a project;
- To be able to function effectively as an individual and a team member;
- To be able to communicate effectively with the engineering community and with experts from different fields;
- To be able to independently organise and manage personal learning process in the context of life-long learning.

In addition, we defined the pedagogical objectives and learning outcomes for students working on projects, which made it possible to determine the most urgent pedagogical issues and, after the finishing of the project, to assess the efficiency of chosen learning approaches. Some of the pedagogical objectives and related learning outcomes are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Example of pedagogical objectives and relative learning outcomes

Pedagogical objectives	Learning outcomes
Contextualisation of the learning process through the creation of the conditions close to professional ones including interaction with customers and teamwork	To be able to formulate an engineering problem and choose an appropriate method of solution; ability to communicate effectively with experts from different fields
To provide the involvement of students in the creation of own learning trajectory	To be able to independently organise and manage learning process in the context of life-long learning
To provide student involvement in information search and processing when working with ill-defined problems	To be able to conduct searches of literature, and to use different sources of information, analyse and verify information
Enable students to use modern project management approaches (e.g. Agile-methods) in own projects	To be able to carry out planning, management and completion of a project
Encourage students to propose own engineering solution and ideas (e.g. in the form of a start-up) and to take part in competitions and grant programmes	To be able to estimate implementation potential of own products as real-life application
Encourage students to participate in scientific research	To be able to recognise the importance and perspectives of scientific research

Organization of students' projects: topics choosing

The choice of topics for student projects is influenced by several factors:

- current relations between the university and local businesses;
- limited financial resources of the university;
- students' own interests.

For a certain period, the ACIT educational programme has been aimed at the training of engineers in the field of automation of production processes. However, the economic

developments in the last 10-15 years have significantly influenced the industry pattern of our region, with the IT sphere undergoing a notable boost. Local business is dominated by small and medium-sized enterprises focusing on mid-term projects and the development of a wide range of automation systems. Accordingly, there is a demand for the training of specialists who can develop cyber-physical systems. With short-term industrial placement programmes being the main form of cooperation that small and medium-sized local businesses have with our university, the choice and organisation of projects often mean searching for potential partners elsewhere.

The authors propose a feasible way of topic selection for student projects by organising collaboration in the academic sphere. The academic staff of the Department of ACIT collaborates with the colleagues from the departments of Physics, Biology, Applied Mathematics, Mathematics, and Econometrics etc. Such contacts provide opportunities for generating ideas for projects of senior engineering students. In order to introduce multidisciplinary projects and engage the students and faculty from other departments, a local pilot survey was carried out by the authors in 2015 at BKNUC. The survey involved 37 members of academic staff of the Institute of Information and Educational Technologies. The results of this survey show that 73% of teachers are ready to be facilitators of student teams, and 27% prefer individual forms of student activity. In addition, the respondents were asked to choose the team type – with representatives from other specialities, without them or a team which includes students from closely related specialities. 62.3% of respondents preferred to work with a team of students from related specialities; 32.4% were ready to work with multidisciplinary teams and 5.3% preferred teams without representatives from other specialities. 56.8% of surveyed teachers were ready to collaborate with colleagues from other departments as co-facilitators of student projects regardless of project themes and 43.2% preferred topics which support their research interests. In general, the results of this survey demonstrate that academic staff are open to new educational initiatives fostering the implementation of student projects.

According to the level of involvement, teachers from different departments could act as co-facilitators of teams of students or as "customers". The latter role is very important because it opens an opportunity for students to act in a professional way, analysing the needs of the customer and defining what exactly is needed to solve a particular problem. Such collaboration also partially solves the issues with the limited financing available for student projects.

Another decisive factor in the choice of student project topics is that most of the senior undergraduate students are or become employed during their final year at university. This inevitably reduces the time they can spend doing the projects, especially if it is outside of their current area of interest, the level of motivation may also decline.

2 PROJECTS BASED ON COLLABORATION IN ACADEMIC SPHERE

Teachers of Ukrainian engineering departments are well aware of the intensive development of emerging technologies, such as the Internet of Things – a net of interconnected smart physical objects which includes embedded sensors and software providing data communication and exchange between real-world and computer tools. It seems reasonable that engineering projects of ACIT students involve the design of DAQ systems and various application-based software. One of the constraints was that the designed products should be usable for experts from different fields. Respectively, LabVIEW was chosen as the element of the human-computer interface which allows to carry out the acquisition of data in a continuous cycle, its processing and presentation in a suitable form. In order to minimise the cost of student projects, we use available equipment or low-cost elements like Arduino programmable

microcontroller boards. Project tasks include the design of DAQ system, coordination of processes of data acquisition and processing, and demonstration at runtime.

One of the first examples of a student project was the design of DAQ systems in which the thermocouple L (chromel-copel) was used in order to provide precise measurement of temperature. The challenges for the students were as follows: to analyse the physical and technical aspects of temperature measurements; to choose the type of thermocouple with regard to the previously defined constraints and to provide the correct voltage-temperature conversion; to provide the conversion of measured data to digital format; to write a program for microcontroller initiating the measurements after obtaining the signal from PC and reading of data from the converter and sending to PC; to write a LabVIEW program with the possibility of measurement initiation and processing of measured data. In addition, it was necessary to design a user interface to present the measured data in a suitable form.

In the case of this project, students used built-in VISA modules. Engineering and physics students used the designed system during laboratory works in the course of thermodynamics, e.g. in the investigation of specific heat of liquids when the liquid is heated by use of an electric current. The special LabVIEW VIs was written and during the laboratory works second-year students had a possibility to initiate the process of measurement as well as save and analyse the obtained data. Moreover, a special laboratory work guide was written.

In 2014, we started to use Arduino in student projects. The availability of LabVIEW Interface for Arduino (LIFA), which is the API based on the conception of virtual instruments, was among the advantages of Arduino. In the presented example (Fig. 2) the digital sensor DHT11 which contains a calibrated digital signal output of the temperature and humidity was used.

Fig. 2. An example of designed block-diagram of Arduino-based system

One more interesting practically oriented project was carried out as answer for inquiry from Another interesting practically oriented project was carried out in response to an inquiry from the researchers of the Institute of Natural Sciences. The task was to design a system capturing the digital images of some biological samples placed on a glass plate and process these images according to the requirements of the researchers. Such processing included the calculation of statistical parameters, the area of investigated objects etc. The biological microscope and digital camera were used. Firstly, students used the Ni Vision Assistant, in which special sketches were developed. The next challenge of the project was to design LabVIEW VI in which a wide range of tools and functions were used in order to process the series of images (Fig. 3).

Since the products were designed for use in research and learning practice, the development of clear instructions for the designed system (which conditions are necessary to carry out the measurements, typical errors, demands related to hardware etc.) was a compulsory task.

Fig. 3. An example of designed block-diagram of digital image processing

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The presented learning activity has become a certain reference point for academic staff and students. The formal integration of the introduced changes to the educational programme is in progress. Overall, the employment of practically oriented team-based projects has received positive perception among the academic staff of the Department of ACIT as well as among our colleagues from other departments.

All difficulties which emerged during the implementation of student projects could be divided into two categories. The first one is related to learning aspects such as a transparent and appropriate system of assessment of student activity both individually and in a team. In order to overcome such difficulties, we proposed a form of assessment which includes evaluation of the process of project design (log-book, mid-term report), peer-review of text (content, style and structure), presentation, and answers to questions. The second category of difficulties was related to administrative and organisational issues, like the formal definition of the workload of teachers from different departments, budget-planning for the student projects etc. We also observed special moments related to the interaction between students and teachers who acted as the "customers" of the designed systems. In the case of facilitators, it was very important to find the balance and help the students to organise direct communication with these teachers. One of the problem points with the search for student project supervisors was that faculty members from different departments were ready to act as such only if the projects lay within the area of their scientific interest.

At present, a lack of project management skills is very notable. Students also indicated that they experienced difficulties with time management and when working with information. Additionally useful was the opportunity to observe and to analyse student behaviour in terms of the economic aspects of the projects. Although the students demonstrated responsibility in financial planning, they were less confident in making the final decisions. At this stage, they needed additional consultations with the facilitators.

4 SUMMARY

The development of computer-aided data acquisition multipurpose systems which could also be used in scientific research and education, enables contextualisation of the learning process when students develop competencies concurrently with the solution of real-world problems. Students involved in the projects have noted positive perception of own activity. They were enthusiastic about the possibility to design real things and to observe how these things could

be used in research and learning. Students who were involved in the projects took part in the annual student conference hosted by our university.

5 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The one of the authors (G.V. Lutsenko) would like to acknowledge the support by the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine (#0117U003909).

REFERENCES

- [1] Maffioli, F., Augusti, G. (2003). Tuning engineering education into the European higher education orchestra. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, Vol.28, No. 3, pp. 251-273.
- [2] Heitmann, G. (2005). Challenges of engineering education and curriculum development in the context of the Bologna process. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, Vol. 30, No. 4, pp. 447-458.
- [3] SCM. (2012). *Graduates of Ukrainian Higher Educational Institutions: Stakeholders View*. Retrieved from https://www.yourcompass.org/docs/Employees%20on%20University_Graduates.pdf
- [4] SCM. (2013). *Employment Experience of Higher Educational Institutions Graduates: Stakeholders and Graduates View*. Retrieved from <http://www.slideshare.net/bestuniverua/ss-27208268>.
- [5] Lucenko, G. V., & Popovychenko, A. A. (2012). Online physical experiments. *Information Technologies and Learning Tools*, 29(3).
- [6] Lutsenko, G. V. (2013). Application of LabVIEW during the processing of experimental data by statistical methods. *Information Technologies and Learning Tools*, 35(3), 120-134.
- [7] Lutsenko, G. V. (2017). Collaborative projects for engineering students. *Science and Education a New Dimension*, 61(141), 41-44.
- [8] De Graaf, E., & Kolmos, A. (2003). Characteristics of problem-based learning. *International Journal of Engineering Education*, Vol. 19, No. 5, pp. 657-662.
- [9] Kolmos, A. (1996). Reflection on Project Work and Problem-Base Learning. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, Vol. 21, No. 2, pp. 141-148.
- [10] Kolmos, A., de Graaff, E., & Du, X. (2009). Diversity of PBL – PBL learning principles. y X. Du, E. de Graaff, & A. Kolmos (Ред.), *Research on PBL Practice in Engineering Education* (cc. 9-21). Rotterdam: Sense.
- [11] Zakharchenko, V. M., Lugovyi, V. I., Rashkevych, Y. M., & Talanova, Z. V. (2014). *Guide to Development of Degree Programmes*. Kyiv: DP NVC Priorityty.
- [12] OECD. (2011). *A Tuning-AHELO Conceptual Framework of Expected Desired/Learning Outcomes in Engineering*. OECD Education Working Papers, No. 60, OECD Publishing. doi:10.1787/5kghtchn8mbn-en